

Parents' Social Variables and Youths' Dispirit for Tertiary Education in Anambra State, Nigeria

*Onwuhanze, Jude Uche Ph.D.¹

Adiewere, Alex Ngozi¹

Ajuru, Sebastine Ugwuanyi¹

¹Department of Educational Management, College of Education, Michael Okpara University, Umudike, Abia State

Abstract

The study examined the influence of parents' social variables on youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated to aid the study. The study adopted an ex post facto design. The population consisted of 934,825 youths in Anambra State. Sample of 1110 youths were selected for the study through purposive sampling technique. Data for the study were collected using a researcher developed instrument known as Parents' Social Variables and Youths Dispirit Questionnaire (PSVYDQ). The instrument was validated by three experts before the reliability test was conducted with 40 respondents who were not part of the sample. Cronbach Alpha was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. The instrument has an alpha reliability coefficient of 0.88 for youth dispirit for university education. Data collected were analyzed using analysis of variance at 0.05 level of significance. The result of data analysis for all the hypotheses were significant and therefore the null hypotheses were rejected. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that parents' social variables have significant influence on youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra state. It was therefore recommended among others that sociologists of education and other spirited individuals and organizations should organized orientation programmes aimed at discouraging divorce, and child-birth before marriage especially among financially dependent youths. If marriages are helped to remain united, couples will be more likely to encourage their children to aspire for tertiary education.

Keywords: Youths dispirit, marital status and tertiary education

Introduction

In Nigeria, the consciousness of becoming graduates by both male and female students pervades anxiety for admission into foreign and local universities. Academic programmes learned in the tertiary institutions are designed to take cognizance of the needs of the society and the individuals. They are geared towards making the graduates functional in the society. Generally, tertiary education is seen as a means by which the societal needs and aspirations could be attained through the courses in the curriculum. Some of the advantages of the tertiary education include but not limited to assisting graduates to live a fuller and richer life and making them grow in knowledge and wisdom, as well as helping them develop some aesthetic sense and value (Okey-kalu, 2019). Some other scholars such as Olamide, and Tobiloba (2022) describe university education as a way of preserving the future and the way of life in which a people believe in as well as the modest way to live a comfortable life. It is seen as an essential channel for development if a society has to survive.

However, tertiary education, whether polytechnic, college of education or university education, has their own challenges, it may be seen to be difficult and demands endurance; it sometimes deprive undergraduates of social and freedom to roam about because of academic work load (Adams, 2019). Again, the Nigerian university system has been imperiled by misconceived government policies and poor funding; incessant disruption of academic activities; lack of employment opportunities for prospective graduates and so forth (Ali, 2021; Olaleye, 2022). Olaleye (2022) noted that only one percent of the total population pursues higher education. The uncertainties faced by many Nigerian youths over their future occasioned by incessant strikes and the decay of public institutions seem to contributes to discouraging many youths for aspiring for the university education. For example, the eight-month long strike of Non-Academic Staff Union of Universities, from February 14, to October 13, 2022, forced many youths in many universities to pick up skills to pass time and seek employment to earn a living. Moreover, Olaleye (2022) asserted that due to the rise in non-conventional jobs, tertiary education might seem unnecessary. According to Arnhold (2021), some people believed that you do not need a degree to learn almost anything on the internet. Adams (2019) in his study found that nearly two third of respondents are interested in doing an apprenticeship rather than going to university after leaving school. Due to low wages, graduate jobs that might have been prestigious or well-paid three decades ago are now bottom of the career ladder. Often a young person could go straight into work, get promoted, and then be earning significantly more money than they would be if they got into the same field after university (Preddy, 2019).

Parents' Social Variables and Youths ... (Onwuhanze, et al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370752>

Most authors like Kalu (2019), Olaleye (2022) and Arnhold (2021) agreed that the level of parents' involvement in the schooling of their children is a significant indicator of the quality of schooling. This study investigates parent's educational qualifications and parents' marital status as family social variables that may influence youths dispirit for tertiary education especially the university education. Parents' educational qualifications is the combination of knowledge, skills, understanding and attainment of the youths' parents in an organized and accepted educational institution. It is classified as a formal education, First School Leaving Certificate, Senior Secondary Certificate, Ordinary National Diploma, Bachelor Degree, Masters, Doctorate Degree, among others. Marital status is the parents' recognized position in the society in terms of marriage. Youths dispirit refers to the youths' lack of enthusiasm toward furthering their tertiary education because they are depressed and dejected. Various researchers and authors are in agreement with the direct association of parents' literacy level with children's academic achievements and their decision to leave school (Tsolou & Babalis, 2020). Wulansari, Lisnawati, Sahid, wahyudi, (2023) asserts that parents' factors are very important in their children's educational interest. According to Gobena (2018) if learners are to maximize their potential from schooling, they will need the full support of their families.

Parental education has strong implications for parental orientations toward their children's achievement (Mortimer, 2015). Low literacy level leads to vicious cycle of illiteracy (Chugh, 2011) and children coming from educated families are reported to show high academic achievement and educational attainments (Tsolou & Babalis, 2020). Gobena (2018) found that children whose families are of high education scales have shown statistically far better changes of participating in tertiary education. Poorly educated parents usually earn low income, as a result, would not be able to sponsor the cost of qualitative education for their children (Ahmed, & Abdalrahman, 2022). Mortimer, (2015) found that financially strapped parent with the highest level of education may be especially concerned that their children maintain high expectation for the future despite transient economic difficulties. In contrast poorly educated parents appear to be the more vulnerable, as they are likely the most threatened by economic hardship. With the most limited prospect in labor market, their opportunities to improve their families' economic positions may be the most constrained. Children who observe their parents' plight may become discouraged, lessening their confidence in the economic realm.

Marital status classified people as divorced, widowed or in a relationship. A person is said to be divorced if he or she has officially ended his/her marriage to someone; widowed if his/his wife/husband is dead (Gobena et'al 2018). The level of instability in the home environment is also important to adolescents' academic career (Aguboshim, 2021). The cumulative effect of the loss or addition of a parental figure in the home may disrupt a child's sense of security and have negatively affected children's academic aspirations. Because of time constraints, dwindling assistance, new obligations, and the possible strain introduced to the parent-child relationship by divorce or start of a parent's new romantic relationship; single parents and those who are married to or are cohabiting with new partners may experience less closeness with their adolescents despite their best effort (Aguboshim, 2021). If children do not feel close to their parents, or if parents are not able to supervise their children's lives, parents influence on school achievement and course-taking decision may be undermined. Family disruptions may cause young people to be less optimistic about their future including their prospects of attending tertiary institutions (Gobena, 2018). Nanteza, Nasasira, Nabawanda and Katike (2021) in their study found that marital status has no direct effect on children's academic progress because it did not offer leverage in explaining how family instability related to students' academic factors like income and parental expectations.

A closer observation shows that in order to acquire wealth in their youthful age, some youths have become more interested in acquiring vocational occupation. The display of wealth, and the number of houses and vehicles owned by many business merchants and contractors who are not educated up to the tertiary education seems to impress the youths in Anambra State and believe that business without tertiary education is the quickest way to prosperity (Adams 2019). Ordinarily, this is not bad on itself but the future consequences of this should rather be imagined than seen. If this trend is not checked, the resultant effects will be that, in the nearest future Anambra State will have shortage of educated professionals to represent her in different fields of human endeavours both in Nigerian and in the world in general. There will equally be shortage of teachers from the primary to the tertiary levels. The State will retrogress to pre-colonial era where illiteracy reigns supreme. Against this background, the study is aimed at examining whether parents' social variables have any influence on youths dispirit for tertiary education.

The findings of this study are hoped to add more to the existing body of knowledge in helping parents and youths to develop interest in tertiary education and for the light the study throws on parents' variables and youth dispirit for tertiary education. Further research related to this topic will also be facilitated.

Objectives of the Study

Parents' Social Variables and Youths ... (Onwuhanze, et al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370752>

The main objective of this study was to determine how parents' social variables can influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the influence of parents' educational qualification on youths dispirit for tertiary education.
2. Determine the influence of parent's marital status on youths dispirit for tertiary education

Research Questions

1. To what extent does parents' educational qualification influences youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State?
2. What is the extent to which parent's marital status influences youth dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance:

1. Parents' educational qualifications do not significantly influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State.
2. Parents' marital status does not significantly influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State.

Methodology

This study adopted ex post facto design. It is a systematic enquiry in which the researcher has no control over the independent variables because, their manifestations have already occurred. The population for study was 934,825 young people between the ages of 14 and 24 years. A total of 1,110 youths were selected from the population as samples for the study using the purposive sampling technique. This technique was used because the researcher had no exert population of youths in each senatorial district in Anambra State who are not in any tertiary institution. Data for the study were obtained using a researcher-developed instrument known as Parents' Social Variables and Youths Dispirit Questionnaire (PSVYDQ). The instrument has two sections labeled section A & section B. Section A collected information on the respondents' parents' educational qualification and marital status, while section B collected information on youths dispirit for tertiary education (12 items). The questionnaire, which was validated by two Measurement experts, had a reliability coefficient of 0.88. The hypotheses were tested using analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. If the calculated result is greater than the critical value at .05 level of significance, reject the null hypothesis, but otherwise retain the null hypothesis. The data were analyzed using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and dependent t-test.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does parents' educational qualification influences youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean scores of the influence of parents' educational qualifications on youths 'dispirit for tertiary education

Parents' Educational Qualifications	N	Mean
No formal education/FSLC	410	36.35
SSCE/GCE	434	36.15
OND/NCE	81	33.71
Bachelor Degree/HND/PGD	115	34.04
Masters and Above	70	33.51

The data presented in Table 1 show the mean scores of the influence of parents' educational qualifications on youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State. This simply shows that youths whose parents have no formal education have the highest mean score of 36.35 for youths dispirit for tertiary education while those parents' educational qualification is masters and above had the lowest mean score of 33.51 for youths dispirit for tertiary education.

Research Question Two

What is the extent to which parent's marital status influences youth dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State's

Parents' Social Variables and Youths ... (Onwuhanze, et al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370752>

Table 2: Mean scores of the influence of parents' marital status on youths dispirit for tertiary education

Parents' Educational Qualifications	N	Mean
Unmarried	129	34.18
Married	613	33.63
Widowed	334	33.63
Divorced	134	35.71

The data presented in Table 2 show the influence of marital status on youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State. Youths dispirit is higher among youths whose parents are divorced having a mean score of 35.71, followed by the unmarried parents (34.18).

Hypothesis 1

Parents' educational qualifications does not significantly influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance of the influence of parents' educational qualifications on youths dispirit for tertiary education

Sources of variance	SS	df	MS	F
Between Groups	519.2	4	129.8	8.85
Within Groups	16207.47	1105	14.67	

Level of significant = .05, critical value = 1.73

The data presented in Table 3 reveal the obtained F-value of 8.85. This value was tested for significance by comparing it with the critical F-value of 1.73 at .05 level of significance. The observed f-value was greater than the critical value of 1.73. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that parents' educational qualifications do not significantly influence youths dispirit for university education is rejected.

Hypothesis 2

Parents' marital status does not significantly influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State.

Table 4: Analysis of Variance of the influence of parents' marital status on youths dispirit for tertiary education

Sources of variance	SS	df	MS	F
Between Groups	166.18	3	55.39	3.21
Within Groups	19097.55	1105	17.27	

Level of significant = .05, critical value = 1.73

The result of the analysis of variance presented in Table 4 show that the calculated F-value of 3.21 is greater than F-critical value of 1.73 at .05 level of significance. The null hypothesis which states that parents' marital status does not significantly influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State is therefore rejected.

Discussions of Findings

The result of data analysis in Table 3 was significant due to the fact that the obtained F-value (8.85) was greater than the critical F-value (1.73) at .05 level of significance. This implies that there is significant influence of parents' educational qualifications on youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra state. Youths whose parents' highest educational qualification is first school leaving certificate (FSLC) were more dispirited than youths whose parents' highest education qualification was Master and above. This means that the lower the level of parents' educational qualifications, the higher the youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra state. This finding agrees with the studies of Chugh (2011) and (Tsolou & Babalis, 2020) that Low literacy level leads to vicious cycle of illiteracy and children coming from educated families show high academic achievement and educational attainments. The study also supports the findings of Gobena (2018), and Ahmed, and Abdalrahman (2022) that children whose families are of high education scales have a statistically far better changes of participating in tertiary education. Poorly educated parents usually earn low income, as a result, would not be able to sponsor

Parents' Social Variables and Youths ... (Onwuhanze, et al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370752>

the bills of qualitative education for their children. The study is in agreement with Mortimer, et'al (2015) that financially strapped parent with the highest level of education may be especially concerned that their children maintain high expectation for the future despite transient economic difficulties.

The result of the data analysis in Table 4 was significant due to the fact that the obtained F-value (3.21) was greater than the critical F-value (1.73) at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that there is significance influence of parents' marital status on youth dispirit for Tertiary education in Anambra State. Moderately stronger influence was found among youths whose parents are divorced (35.71) and moderately weak influence was found among youths whose parents are intact married couple (33.63). This means that youth whose parents are divorced and unmarried are more likely to be dispirited than youths whose parents are intact married partners. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Aguboshim (2021)) that the cumulative effect of the loss or addition of a parental figure in the home may disrupt a child's sense of security, and have negative implication for children's academic aspirations. The study agrees with Gobena (2018) that family disruptions may cause young people to be less optimistic about their future including their prospects of attending tertiary institutions. However, the study disagrees with the findings of Nanteza, et'al (2021) that marital status has no direct effect on children's academic progress.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, conclusions were drawn that social variables of parents' level of education and marital status significantly influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra state. Parents have remarkable role to play in determining the educational aspiration of their children or youths. Youths whose parents have lower educational qualifications and those whose parents are not married or divorced are more likely to show lack of enthusiasm to tertiary education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government and the non-governmental organizations should organize a behavioural change awareness campaign to enlighten parents on the importance of supporting youths to acquire tertiary education.
2. Sociologists in Education and Guidance Counsellors should organize orientation programmes aimed at discouraging divorce among married couples, and child birth before marriage especially among financially dependent youths.

References

- Adams, R. (2019). Young people more skeptical of need to go to university. Retrieved on December 27, 2022 from <https://www.theguardian.com/education>.
- Aguboshim, F. C. (2021)). Parental marital status influence on academic performance in TT subjects of In-school Adolescents in Nigeria. *International Journal of Engineering Management and Economics* 13 (2), 494-500
- Ahmed, O. S. & Abdalrahman, E. (2022). The relationship between social variables related to parents and the academic achievement of their children during coronavirus: A case study. *Journal of information sciences* 11(3), 739-744
- Ali, Y. (2021). Tertiary Education and the future of Nigeria. A convocation lecture delivered on 22nd October 2021, at the University of Ilorin. Retrieved on January31, 2023 from <https://yusufali.net/article/tertiary-education-and-the-future-of-nigeria>
- Arnhold, N (2021) tertiary education overview: World Bank group reporter. Retrieved on January31, 2022 from <http://www.worldbank.org/>.
- Gobena, G. (2018). Family socio-economic status on Students' Academic Achievement at college of Education and behavioural sciences Haramaya University, Eastern Ethiopia. *Journal of Teacher Education and Educators* 7(3), 207-222
- Mortimer, J. t. Zhang, F. L., Hussamann, J, & Wu, C (2015). Parental Economic Hardship and children's Achievement Orientation. *Longit Life Course Studies* 5(2), 105-128
- Nanteza, S., Nasasira, D., Nabawanda, F., & Katike, R. M. (2021). Parental Socio-economic status, parental marital status and pupils' academic performance among pupils in Kawempe Divisiob, Kampala District. Retrieved on December 28, 2022 from <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.1228/9467>
- Okey-kalu, O. (2019). The importance of tertiary education in Nigeria. Retrieved on January31,2022 from <http://www.tetedia.com/the-importance-of-tertiary-education>

Parents' Social Variables and Youths ... (Onwuhanze, et al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370752>

- Olaleye, P. O. (2022). Are Gen-Zs Losing Interest in Tertiary Education in Nigeria? Retrieved on January 31, 2023 from <http://www.nigeria.appliedworldwide.com>
- Olamide. L. & Tobiloba A. (2022). Improving the quality of tertiary education in Nigeria. Retrieved from <http://www.businessday.ng/opinion/article/improving-the-quality-of-tertiary-education-in-Nigeria.com>
- Preddy, I. (2019). Why fewer Young People are going to the University. Retrieved on December 28, 2022 from <http://blog.hr.com/blog/why-fewer-young-people-are-going-to-university>
- Tsuolou, O. and Babalis, T. (2020). The contribution of Family Factors to Dropping Out of School in Greece. *Journal of Creative Education* 11(8), 1375-1401. doi:104236/ce.2020.118101
- Wulansari, E., Lisnawati, Sahid, N.,wahyudi, R. (2023). Factors Affecting Students interest in Continuing Study at Higher Education. *International Journal of Education and Teaching* 2(1) Doi:10.570921/ijetz.02i1.116.